

Emergence of Robust Cooperative States by Iterative Internalizations of Opponents' Personalized Values in Minority Game

Takashi Sato

Abstract: Adolescence is a period in which individuals begin facing some challenging choices. Through these choices, and social interactions with peers, adolescent individuals develop their "personalized values" that are the foundations of their actions. It is known that the adolescent brains have high plasticity, and that the adolescent brains change dynamically, other than that of an adult brain. This study discusses the type of behavior that emerges from adolescents, as well as adult individuals with elevated plasticities. To realize this, we adopt the minority game (MG), which is one of the tasks concerning the choice described above. We implement Elman-nets with different learning rates that express different degrees of the plasticity as the player models in the MG. Our simulation results showed that it is a possibility that robust cooperative states emerge by iteratively internalizing the opponent players' personalized values among players that have a network of reference relationship, irrespective of their varying degrees of plasticity.

Keywords: Emergence of Robust Cooperative States; Personalized Values; Minority Game; Elman-net; Adolescence; Adulthood; Plasticity

I. INTRODUCTION

Throughout our lives, we make various choices. In many cases, we try to make good choices that will be profitable, through predictions based on previous experiences and past information that we have obtained. Such predictions, however, do not always lead to good choices. In some cases, whether a choice is good or bad is determined by the result of combined choices that many people have made. Therefore, a prediction to make an appropriate choice will be more difficult, like the Keynesian beauty contest [8] and the El Farol Bar problem [1].

Adolescence is a period in which individuals start facing difficult choices, and is a phase between late childhood and adulthood. By making choices, through social interactions with peers, and by internalizing and personalizing other individuals' values, the adolescent individuals develop their "personalized values," that are the foundations of their actions [6-7]. Moreover, it is a characteristic of adolescent individuals to be prone to risky-behavior [12-13]. It is also known that adolescent brains have high plasticity that dynamically change their brains, including synapses, neurons, and axons [4-5,14]. Konrad et al [9] suggest that there is a possibility that typical adolescent behavior patterns, including risk-taking, are caused by the high plasticity of the adolescent brain.

The minority game (MG) [2] is one of the tasks

concerning the choices described above, and a simplified model of the El Farol Bar problem [1]. Our previous study [11] which adopted the MG, found that 101 players who act by referring to opponents' past actions in the MG, formed a ratio of 50 minority to 51 majority with high frequency. Thus, cooperative states in the group of players emerged. This result suggests that cooperative states are caused by indirectly sharing personalized values which are actuating factors of the opponents among each connected player, and internalizing the values by the time-series learning of the opponent's past states.

In that study [11], we adopted the Elman-net [3] as a learning player model with a very low learning rate. The Elman-net is one of the recurrent neural network models that can learn and predict a time-series of states. In the case that a very low learning rate is set, the rate of change in the Elman-net in the learning process is also very small. This means that the plasticity of the network is low. Therefore, the Elman-net with low plasticity can be regarded as a model of adult individuals. This study, however, has not yet examined what kind of behavior will emerge in the MG using an adolescent model with high plasticity.

The purpose of this study is to clarify what kind of behavior will emerge in the MG when using an adolescent model with high plasticity, and comparing the results of the model with that of the adulthood model with low plasticity.

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In order to realize the purpose, we adopt the Elman-nets with different learning rates that express different types of the plasticities as player models in the MG.

II. MINORITY GAME AND ELMAN-NET AS ITS GAME PLAYER

A. Minority game

We adopt a "minority game (MG) [2]", which can be regarded as one of the tasks concerning difficult choices encountered repeatedly in the course of life. This game was proposed by Challet and Zhang [2]. They are inspired by the El Farol bar problem introduced by Arthur [1].

The El Farol bar problem [1] is based on the assumption that there is a bar with a capacity of 100 people, when the number is 60 or less, it is not congested, and when it is over 60 people, it becomes crowded and uncomfortable. If the current number of people in the bar is less than 60 people, we decide to go to the bar. However, when there are more than 60 people in the bar, we should not go to the bar. In short, the minority can gain a profit. Arthur [1] claims that the rationality of human beings is limited, modeled individuals' existence predicting behavior based on the past history, and discussed the bounded rationality of people using this bar problem.

The MG is a model that simplified the above problem, and characterized it by the following two basic rules; (1) N (odd) players must choose one out of two alternatives (e.g. -1/1 meaning buy/sell, etc.) independently at each step. (2) Those who are on the minority side win, and gain a point. We call this flow from (1) to (2) "one step." All players learn a time series of the information for the past o steps per every p steps. We refer to p steps as "one turn."

The schematic view and the procedure of the MG in our simulation are illustrated in Fig. 1 and 2, respectively.

Fig. 1. The schematic view of the MG in our simulation.

In this study, we investigate the effect of three types of the information that players receive, based on the result of

Fig. 2. The procedure of the MG in our simulation.

the MG; (1) the past minority hand formed by all players' hands as the macro information, (2) the past hand of the opponent player, and (3) the past hand of the player him- or herself. Therefore, we prepare three kinds of players, each of whom receives information separately. The details of these player models are described in section B.

B. Elman-net as the game player

Arthur [1] argued that when individuals make certain decisions, they will act by predicting the next situation based on, not only last-minute information, but also on historical information. The study proposes that processing the time-series of information plays a key role in making decisions. Therefore, we adopt an Elman-net [3] as the player model of the MG. The Elman-net is one of the recurrent neural network models which have the ability to learn and predict a time-series data.

The basic architecture of the Elman-net consists of four layers: An input layer to accept external information; an output layer to decide the output values based on the information; a hidden layer to process input values and to pass them to the output layer; and a context layer, in which each neuron has one-to-one connections with each neuron of the hidden layer. The architecture of the three types of player models with different information sources are illustrated in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. The three types of the MG player models adopted in our simulation.

Fig. 4. Ranked each player's total score of three models with four kinds of learning rates (0.01, 0.1, 0.5, and 0.8). The x-axis is the rank number ranged from 1 (left side) to 101 (right side). The y-axis is the total score ranged from 0 to 850,000. "Macro," "Opponent" and "Self" mean the player model (a)-(c), respectively.

III. SIMULATIONS

A. Settings of simulations

Before describing the results of the simulations, the specifications of the simulations are listed. In the simulations, the population size of the players are set to 101. Each simulation is conducted for 100 turns, where 10,000 steps are referred to as 1 turn. Therefore, one simulation consists of 1,000,000 steps.

The Elman-nets of each player have one output neuron, five hidden neurons (i.e. context neurons) and one input neuron. The nonlinear strength of output function in the Elman-net is 0.8. By using the error backpropagation learning algorithm, each player independently learns a time series of the historical information for the past 100 steps for every 10,000 steps. As mentioned above, the input values that the player model (a)-(c) learn in the learning process, are the past minority hands, the past hands of the opponent's player, and the past hands of the player him- or herself, respectively. Their teacher signals are also the time series of the past minority hands corresponding to the input values. A learning process is completed when the total errors between teacher signals and outputs of a player became

less than 0.01, or the maximum number of learning iteration reached at 10,000.

In order to represent the low plasticity of the brain in adulthood, and the high plasticity of the brain in adolescence, and to verify the effects of the differences between these plasticities on the results of MG, we employ four values of the learning rate (Lrate); 0.01, 0.1, 0.5, and 0.8.

At the beginning of the simulation, in each Elman-net, all the input values including the feedback input values from the output, and the hidden neurons, are set to 0.0. The initial connection weights are set to random real numbers between -0.5 and 0.5, and only recurrent connection weights are fixed at 1.0. Only player model (b) randomly selected an opponent player in the population at the first step, and does not change opponents until the last step.

B. Results of the simulations

<Comparison of the total scores>

First, we compare each player's total score in each model with different learning rates. These results are illustrated in Fig. 4, where the x-axis is the rank number ranged from 1 (left side) to 101 (right side), and the y-axis is the total score ranged from 0 to 850,000. The terms "Macro," "Opponent" and "Self" in Fig. 4 mean player models (a)-(c), respectively.

As can be seen at a glance, the graphs of player model (c) are very different from the others. There are two distinct peaks in the graphs when the Lrates are 0.01. As the Lrate increases, the valleys between the two peaks become deeper, the width between them becomes wider, eventually becoming more distorted. The peaks close to the ends of the x -axis mean that most players took the same hand repeatedly. In other words, the number of majority players will be much larger than the number of minority ones.

<Comparison of the average cosine similarities of behaviors>

Third, we analyze the time series of hands, which is the behavioral dynamics of each player, by using the cosine similarity. The cosine similarity is a measure of similarity calculated by using the cosine of the angle formed by the two vectors. A similarity of two players' behaviors is calculated by

$$S(\vec{q}, \vec{d}) = \frac{\sum_{i=0}^k q_i d_i}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=0}^k q_i^2} \cdot \sqrt{\sum_{i=0}^k d_i^2}} \quad (2)$$

where S is the cosine similarity, and \vec{q} and \vec{d} are the time series of each player's hands represented by the vectors. The data used in the calculation are the time series of players' hands for the last 5,000 steps in each turn. This is because the data for the first 5,000 steps can be regarded as transient. The averages and the standard deviations of the cosine similarities of behaviors formed by each player model are depicted in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. Averages and standard deviations of cosine similarities of the time series generated by three models with four kinds of learning rate (0.01, 0.1, 0.5, and 0.8).

In Fig. 6, the results show that a decreasing Lrate causes an increase in the similarities of time series generated by the player model (b) and (c). By contrast, the similarities of that of the player model (a) when the Lrate is 0.01 become slightly higher,

but the similarities irrespective of all Lrates stay roughly the same.

Models (b) and (c) have a commonality, in that the cosine similarity becomes higher as the Lrate decreases. However, as can be expected from Fig. 5, the structures generated by each model differ greatly. When the Lrate is 0.01, the highest occurrence frequency of the ratio between the minority and the majority in model (b) is about 50:51, compared to the ratio in model (c), which is about 40:61, as illustrated in Fig. 5.

In our previous study [11], we hypothesized that cooperative states are caused by indirectly sharing personalized values among players who form a network of reference relationships between the players, having some looped structures, and internalizing the personalized values through the time-series learning of the opponent's past states. This is considering that in case there are the looped structures in the network, it is thought that influences of actions produced by a player are returned to the player him- or herself through the propagation in the loop.

To confirm this hypothesis, we investigate the relationship between network structures and cosine similarities. Fig. 7 shows four examples of the network structures generated in model (b). As mentioned above in section III-A, each player in model (b) randomly selects an opponent player in the players' group at the first step, and does not change opponents until the last step. Therefore, the network structures are also not changed. Fig. 7(1) and 7(2) are examples of networks with a different number of players in the looped structures, although each average cosine similarity (ACS) of both networks is 0.739 and 0.735 respectively, which are high values. Fig. 7(3) and 7(4) are examples of networks with high and low ACSs (0.730 and 0.717), even though both networks have almost the same number of players (17 and 20) in the looped structures. The difference, except for their ACSs in Fig. 7(3) and 7(4), is whether or not the network is divided into separate clusters. These results point toward one of the following two possibilities; 1) the length of the looped structure is of little relevance to whether or not the cosine similarity of behavioral dynamics of players gets higher, and 2) what clusters exist in the network is a cause of the low cosine similarity.

In order to confirm the relationship between the cosine similarity and the existence of clusters in the network, we summarize twenty data sets, including the averages of cosine similarities and their standard deviations, the number of players in the looped structures, and the number of clusters. Table 1 shows the results of the average of cosine similarity in rank order. What this table tells us, is that there is an inversely proportional relationship between the cosine similarity and the number of clusters, with a few exceptions.

Fig. 7. Examples of network structures in the model that each player's hand is determined based on the opponent player's hand. In these networks, the circled numbers represent each player, the arrowed lines express reference relationships between the players, and the red colored parts mean the longest looped structure in the networks. Fig. 7(1) and 7(2) are examples of networks with different number of players in the looped structures, though the average cosine similarity (ACS) of the both networks is high. Fig. 7(3) and 7(4) are examples of networks with the high and low ACSs, though both networks have almost the same number of players in the looped structures. The different point except for their ACSs in Fig. 7(3) and 7(4) is whether or not the network is divided to some clusters.

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<Comparison of the average occurrence rates of complex macro dynamics in the MG>

Next, we investigate the occurrence rates of complex (aperiodic) macro dynamics, namely the time-series of minority hands, for all 100 turns in the three models with different

Table 1. Relationships among the cosine similarities, the number of players in the looped structures and the number of the network clusters. The term CS in the table 1 means the cosine similarity. Note that the network that is constituted only one cluster indicated in red occupies most of the top.

Rank	Ave. of CS	Ave. of S.D. of CS	# of players looped and clusters
1	0.7388	0.0778	12 = 1cluster
2	0.7362	0.0875	8, 3 = 2clusters
3	0.7361	0.0863	5 = 1cluster
4	0.7350	0.0820	6 = 1cluster
5	0.7346	0.0774	12 = 1cluster
6	0.7304	0.0803	17 = 1cluster
7	0.7300	0.0930	8, 6 = 2clusters
8	0.7299	0.0821	3, 11, 7 = 3clusters
9	0.7236	0.0951	8 = 1cluster
10	0.7223	0.0955	7, 2, 2 = 3clusters
11	0.7221	0.0982	7, 2 = 2clusters
12	0.7220	0.0979	3, 5, 2, 2 = 4clusters
13	0.7191	0.0889	6, 4 = 2clusters
14	0.7184	0.0924	12, 6 = 2clusters
15	0.7178	0.0978	2, 4, 2 = 3clusters
16	0.7175	0.0949	2, 4 = 2clusters
17	0.7172	0.0943	12, 7, 6, 3 = 4clusters
18	0.7170	0.0920	2, 20, 3 = 3clusters
19	0.7064	0.0972	10, 2, 4 = 3clusters
20	0.6977	0.1069	2, 6, 3, 5 = 4clusters

learning rates. Fig. 8 tells us the following five things: 1) The occurrence of complex macro dynamics is almost nonexistent in model (a); 2) such dynamics rarely occur in model (b); 3) the occurrence rates stay approximately the same in model (a) and (b), irrespective of all Lrates; 4) in model (c), the occurrence rate of the dynamics increases as the Lrate decreases; and 5) the standard deviations of that in model (c) are comparatively large.

Fig. 8. Average numbers and standard deviations of occurrence rate of complex (aperiodic) time-series of minority hand for the all 100 turns, generated by three models with four kinds of learning rate (0.01, 0.1, 0.5, and 0.8).

We also show an example of a part of the complex (aperiodic) macro dynamics generated in model (c), when the

Lrate is 0.01, as illustrated in Fig. 9¹. This shows that the minority hand is dynamically changed per step, and these macro dynamics is thought of as being analogous to dynamics generated by a chaos system. It has not yet been evaluated whether these dynamics can be regarded as chaos.

Fig. 9. An example of the complex (aperiodic) macro dynamics generated in the model that each player acts based on its own self hand when the Lrate is 0.01. The x-axis and the y-axis of each figure are the steps and the minority hands converted to real numbers ranged from 0.0 to 1.0, respectively.

<Comparison of the average success rates of learning>

Last, we compare the average success rates of learning, since the difference among the average occurrence rate of the complex macro dynamics is large, as illustrated in Fig. 8. The results are depicted in Fig. 10. Thus, the success rate of learning in model (a) decreases as the Lrate increase. Moreover, in model (c), the success rates make a little difference, although the average occurrence rate of the complex macro dynamics increases, as the Lrate increases. In contrast, the success rate in model (b) increases as the Lrate decreases. Although the occurrence rates of complex macro dynamics in models (a) and (b) are not dissimilar, the difference of the success rates of learning in these models are nearly double when Lrate is 0.01.

IV. DISCUSSION

<Differences of the influences of macro, opponent and self hands from the viewpoints of the personalized value, and the learning rate expressing the adolescent and adulthood plasticities>

We discuss the differences of the influences of macro, opponent's, and player's own hands from the viewpoints of "personalized value [6-7]," and the

Fig. 10. Average success rate of learning in the three models with four kinds of learning rate (0.01, 0.1, 0.5, and 0.8).

learning rate expressing the adolescent and adulthood plasticities. As mentioned in section I, the personalized value is the foundation of behavior. Values shared in the family and in society is consciously and unconsciously internalized in the brain of the individual. Moreover, internalized values gradually become personalized values unique to the individual, through individualization of values and various experiences [6-7].

By using model (c), we found that a large bias in the ratio of the minority and the majority exists, and the relatively large disparity of total scores is also widened. Model (c) only refers to the past hands of the player him- or herself, in order to predict the trend of macro dynamics made from multiple players, including the individual. This means that, since this model adopts a self-enclosed way of collecting information that does not consider surrounded information other than the past hands of the individual, it is difficult for the players in model (c) to make a favorable prediction based on the information. From this assumption, we can also suppose that almost the players in the model (c) obtain complex personalized values for predicting the macro dynamics through learning repeatedly, since such players cannot win frequently.

The other critical point is the extreme changing results as the Lrate decreases. When setting the Lrate high, which can be regarded as a high plasticity of an adolescent individual, the gap among the players' scores become considerable, and average score is relatively low. In case of a high Lrate, the Elman-nets of each player cannot show a finely tuned response, since the Elman-nets cannot make fine adjustments themselves in the learning process. Therefore, it becomes easier for such players to show naive, rough, and extreme

¹ To draw this graph, we encode the time series of the minority hands. At first, the minority hands, -1 and 1, are coordinated to 0 and 1 as binary digit, respectively. Next, a 20 steps series of the minority hand is regarded as a binary fraction. Then, it is converted to a decimal fraction.

behaviors, like teenagers. However, as the L_{rate} decreases, the degree of similarity of the players' behavioral dynamics increases gradually, and the scores they obtain increase correspondingly, but the occurrence rate of the complex macro dynamics also increases. In our other previous study [10] the MG was adopted, and it was found that the number of players showing aperiodic actions was over 80 percent of the players' group, when the chaotic dynamics is shown at the macro level. From this result, we hypothesize that many players who form the chaos-like macro dynamics shown in this study, have complex personalized values. Because it seems that these players learn useless information in detail to predict the macro dynamics in case of setting the low L_{rate} , they fail to predict the dynamics, and then repeat this process.

From simulation experiments using model (a), we confirmed that the players are less affected by the difference of L_{rates} , as can be seen in Fig. 4~6, and 8. In this model, since all players refer to the past minority hand – namely macro information – in order to predict the macro dynamics, it seems as though it is easy for all players to form personalized values in order to make an appropriate prediction. However, this means that most players will be able to take the same hand, based on the similar personalized value from the same macro information. In the MG, if all players take the same hands, they constitute the majority group, and the whole group loses. In this case, all players learn to take the opposite hands, constituting the majority of the group again. After repeating this learning cycle a few times, the difference in the initial connection weights of the Elman-nets of each player start to influence the formation of their personalized values that emerged through the learning, and the action of each player gradually starts to decrease. It is thought that this is the reason for the bias in the ratio of the majority and the minority, and make it impossible to construct the largest number of winners realized by the ratio of 50 to 51.

What is the significant result showed in model (a)? We specifically, note that in the settings of all L_{rates} , the various types of ratios between the minority to the majority occur relatively uniformly, and the degrees of behavioral similarities are less than that of the other models in most cases, and that the complex macro dynamics hardly emerges. Let us reconsider the influence of a minority hand that is the common teacher signal for all players, based on the significant results shown in model (a). All players of model (a) learn the same time-series of combinations between the past and

the current minority hands. The Elman-net of the player receives the past minority hand as the input data and learns the current minority hand as the teacher signal that is generated by the all players' hands based on the past minority hand. That is to say; the minority hand generated at time step t becomes the teacher signal at time step t and the input data at time step $t+1$. This learning directs all players to take the same behavior, and if everyone takes the same action, it directs all of them to take actions opposite. This resembles that the player learns a data set including inconsistency like "A=B" and "A=C", where the A is the input data, and both the B and the C are the output data that the player must output. It is very difficult for a feedforward type neural network to learn the data set with such inconsistency, and is a bit hard for a recurrent neural network to learn the data set in which many inconsistencies are included. Therefore, in the MG in which such inconsistency is generated over again and again, the players tend to not able to learn and confuse. The success rate of learning in model (a) illustrated in Fig. 10 supports the above speculation.

Compared of these two models, in model (b), the ratio of the minority and the majority population becomes often the ideal form of 50 to 51, and the bias of the total score of each player does not occur comparatively. Each player in model (b) utilizes only a part of the many elements that form the state of the macro level to predict its macro dynamics. Therefore, it is considered difficult to predict the trend of macro dynamics, nonetheless, the reason why the above-described results are earned in model (b) is to have the network of the reference relationship formed by the players. In our previous study [12], we suggested that the looped structure in the network is necessary for making such results, because if the loop exists in the network, each player in the loop can indirectly internalize the opponent player's personalized value by repeatedly learning the time-series of the past hands generated by the opponent player and can also receive influences that the player's own self gave to the others by way of the players in the loop. However, we found that the looped structure is not important, and not having many clusters is important for narrowing the gap among the players from the discussion used the Fig. 7 and the Table 1. A clear distinction among model (b) and the other two models is whether there is the network of the reference relationship among the players. Each player keeps on referring to only one other player selected randomly at first step and learns the past hands of the only one opponent player, but the behavioral feature that the player obtains by referring one

opponent is indirectly propagated from end to end of the network. It is thought that the personalized values of all players in the network become synchronized by little and little by repeating this process.

From the viewpoint of the adolescent (high) and the adulthood (low) plasticities, we found that model (b) is robust, since the scores of the players, the ratio of the minority to the majority, and the occurrence rate of the complex macro dynamics – irrespective of all Lrates – stay approximately the same, as illustrated in Fig. 4, 5 and 8. Moreover, as the Lrate decreases, both of the cosine similarities of the behavioral dynamics among the players and the success rates of learning increased, as depicted in Fig. 6 and 10. The high learning rate, expressing high plasticity of the adolescence, changes significantly the structure of Elman-net. As a result, a player will not be able to learn the complex macro dynamics appropriately, and will thus show rough behavior. When a low learning rate is used, expressing low plasticity as seen in the adulthood contrary to model (a), the success rate of learning in the players of models (b) and (c) increase. However, models (a) and (b) rarely generate complex macro dynamics, however, in model (c), such dynamics occur frequently. These results suggest three things; in model (a), by not being able to successfully learn the patterns of macro dynamics including contradiction, the players will have personalized values that show naive, rough, and extreme behaviors. In model (b), each player indirectly learns personalized values, expressing simple behaviors acquired through learning, and synchronizes these values. In model (c), individualization of personalized value in each player further progresses, and becomes more complicated.

<Emergence of cooperative states based on iterative internalizations of the opponents' personalized values >

Next, we consider the implications of the results generated by the influence of the past information provided by the opponent player. In model (b), the difference between the minority and the majority tends to be small, and the number of winners is close to the maximum, relatively speaking. We suppose that a player will earn 100 profits if he/she wins. If the winner of the game is only one individual, the benefit to the society as a whole will be 100, and if the maximum number of players is 50, and each player wins, the benefit will be 5000. In other words, the more the number of winners, the more it society as a whole benefits.

Since the average total score obtained by the players in model (b) was the highest among the three models, when interpreted based on the above idea, it becomes clear that the information received from the opponent player can be said to be effective information to gain the most profit. Even in the situation where it is difficult to predict the selection of all players, and decide whether each person's choice is good or bad, like the MG, the score difference between players hardly occurred. These results suggest that, among the 101 players, there are few players who will continue to be either winners or losers, and that all the players in the group are bound to benefit. This can be objectively regarded as the emergence of a kind of cooperative state.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we discussed what kind of behavior emerges in the minority game (MG) using an adolescent model with high plasticity, and comparing results of the model with that of an adulthood model with low plasticity. The study adopted the Elman-nets with different learning rates that express different types of plasticities, as the player models in the MG. Furthermore, we verified how the three types of information, namely the past minority hand, the past opponent player's hand, and the past hand of the player him- or herself, given to the players affects the results of the game.

From our simulation results comparing the effects of the learning rate expressing the various plasticities, we confirmed that high learning rate expressing the high plasticity of adolescence, has the effect of easily inducing naive, rough, and extreme behaviors. In contrast, it is a possibility that the low learning rate expressing the low plasticity of adulthood, has some efficacy in creating a kind of cooperative state in the group. This, however, is not the case when including some inconsistency in the learning data and there is a situation that is difficult to learn. Furthermore, we found that, irrespective of the degrees of plasticities, many players can score uniformly, by learning the time series of the opponent player's past hands. Thus, a kind of cooperative states emerges in the group. This result suggests that the robust cooperative states, which is nearly independent of plasticity, are caused by iteratively internalizing the opponent players' personalized values, which are the foundation of their actions, among the players in a network of the reference relationship.

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